

Riemann Zeta Function and Dirichlet Eta Function relating to Alternative Harmonic Series

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Abstract: This paper discusses how the Dirichlet eta function relates to the alternative harmonic series and the Riemann zeta function in more detail. In this article, theorems with proof on the alternative harmonic series and relation between the Dirichlet eta function and the Riemann zeta function are provided to improve the research techniques further in the area of analytic number theory.

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1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series [1-20] with positive exponents served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus [38] and also in the Euler product, the Dirichlet eta function, and the Riemann zeta function. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queueing theory, computer science and medicine [6]. Also, the product of geometric series [21-37] with prime numbers plays a vital role in the sum of natural numbers and harmonic series [39-43].

2. Dirichlet Eta function relating to Alternative Harmonic Series

The harmonic series is defined by

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{9} + \dots$$

and the alternative harmonic series is shown below:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} - \frac{1}{8} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n}.$$

The Dirichlet eta function relating to the alternative harmonic series is defined by

$$\eta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} = 1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} - \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} - \frac{1}{8^s} + \dots$$

The Dirichlet eta function $\eta(s)$ converges for any complex number s and $\text{Re}(s) > 0$.

Theorem 2.1: The sum of alternative harmonic series is equal to $\ln 2$.

$$\text{i.e. } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = \ln 2 \quad \text{OR} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

Proof. This theorem is proved using the infinite geometric series as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } S &= 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots \\ \Rightarrow xS &= x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + x^8 + \dots \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then, } (S - xS) &= 1 \Rightarrow (1 - x)S = 1 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{1 - x} = S. \\ \text{i.e. } \frac{1}{1 - x} &= 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Integrating on both sides with respect to x :

$$\int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx = \int (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots) dx.$$

First, let us find the solution of $\int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx$.

$$\text{Let } u = 1 - x; \quad du = -dx; \quad dx = -du.$$

$$\text{Then, } \int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx = - \int \frac{1}{u} du = - \ln u = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\text{Now, } \int (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots) dx = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\Rightarrow x + \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} + \frac{x^4}{4} + \frac{x^5}{5} + \frac{x^6}{6} + \frac{x^7}{7} + \frac{x^8}{8} + \dots = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n} \dots = - \ln(1 - x) \Rightarrow - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n} = \ln(1 - x).$$

Substituting $x = -1$ on both sides:

$$- \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} = \ln(1 - (-1)) \Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = \ln 2 \quad \text{OR} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

3. Relation between Dirichlet Eta Function and Riemann Zeta Function

The Riemann zeta function for all complex numbers is defined by

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \dots, \quad \forall \operatorname{Re}(s) > 1.$$

The Dirichlet eta function is shown below:

$$\eta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} = 1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} - \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} - \frac{1}{8^s} + \dots$$

The relation between the Dirichlet eta function and the Riemann zeta function is shown below:

$$\textbf{Theorem 3.1: } \eta(s) = (1 - 2^{1-s})\zeta(s) \quad \text{OR} \quad \zeta(s) = \frac{1}{1 - 2^{1-s}} \eta(s)$$

Proof. Let prove this theorem as follows:

$$\zeta(s) - \eta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} = \frac{1}{1^s} - \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \dots$$

$$\zeta(s) - \eta(s) = \frac{2}{2^s} + \frac{2}{4^s} + \frac{2}{6^s} + \frac{2}{8^s} + \frac{2}{10^s} + \frac{2}{12^s} + \dots = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)^s} = \frac{2}{2^s} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}$$

$$\zeta(s) - \eta(s) = 2^{1-s} \zeta(s) \Rightarrow \zeta(s) - 2^{1-s} \zeta(s) = \eta(s).$$

$$\therefore \eta(s) = (1 - 2^{1-s}) \zeta(s) \text{ OR } \zeta(s) = \frac{1}{1 - 2^{1-s}} \eta(s).$$

It is understood that the Dirichlet eta function is the alternative Riemann zeta function.

4. Conclusion

In this article, the author has discussed how the Dirichlet eta function relates to the alternative harmonic series and the Riemann zeta function in detail. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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